

Decolonizing Methodologies and the Reversal of Colonial Logic

Kieran Edmond James

School of Business and Creative Industries, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, UK

Email: kieran.james99@yahoo.co.uk

How to cite this paper: James, K.E. (2023). Decolonizing Methodologies and the Reversal of Colonial Logic. *Advances in Applied Sociology*, 13, 850-867. <https://doi.org/10.4236/aasoci.2023.1311049>

Received: September 28, 2023

Accepted: November 20, 2023

Published: November 23, 2023

Copyright © 2023 by author(s) and Scientific Research Publishing Inc. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Open Access

Abstract

This paper exists as a call for decolonizing methodologies and the reversal of colonial logic. Drawing in part on my own ethnographic research on soccer in the Fiji Islands and popular music and society in Indonesia, I explain how local participants and supporters can and should be encouraged to operate as co-interviewers and co-researchers so that the project has an Indigenous flavour and orientation and functions in terms of Indigenous understandings of relationships, practices and values. I look at how Indigenous myths, often subaltern myths, exist within a mythscape where the governing myth is usually the inherited myth of the colonial power. Subaltern myths and Indigenous ways of knowing combine and I try to illustrate how they differ from European knowledge through the example of the results of a soccer match. Wins against white imperialistic countries enter myth status, while losses are willfully forgotten, and refused entry into the mythscape. A loss that reinforces white European dominance is redundant in the wider scheme of things. It tells us nothing new nor does it empower.

Keywords

Decolonizing Methodologies, European Knowledge, Governing Myth, Indigenous Knowledge, Indigenous Understandings, Mythscape, Subaltern Myths

1. Introduction

In this paper, I set out a perspective and agenda for decolonizing methodologies that draw on my experience as an ethnographer working in the Fiji Islands on soccer history and Indonesia on popular music research. If decolonizing agendas are to have any effect, they require a change of worldview and practices by the researcher and a commitment to empowerment of the Indigenous people. Many

of our subconscious beliefs in the superiority of European ways of knowing (primarily positivistic in method and based on the modernist idea of the individual, rational subject detached from community) and Anglo-American institutions, research culture, and research history (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 38) must be deconstructed (Moosa-Mitha, 2015: p. 75) and challenged (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 37). Challenge can be inspired by sincere and sustained engagement with an Indigenous village or other community and its myriad discourses, values, beliefs, practices, traditions and hierarchies. Many of these aspects of Indigenous social life are remarkably resilient in the face of advancing Westernization and modernization.

In the theoretical field, core-periphery logic is developed in the following way. The Western concept of liberalism, and much more arguably Marxism, cunningly began by the practice of living through a period when the West was perceived to be making advances of a certain type, then labelling the tendency (liberalism, advanced capitalism), and, finally, building a theory about it. That at least some of these features might have occurred earlier in other places, or were simultaneously occurring elsewhere, was shut out of the theoretical and historical frame as the initial labelling was what set the whole process in motion.

As Indigenous studies researcher Linda Tuhiwai Smith (2021: pp. 1-2) says, drawing upon Edward Said (1978: p. 2), the global hegemony of Western ideas of the Orient began thriving in a kind of unholy alliance between academic and popular myths, achieved through continual interaction between the two spheres. Core-periphery logic too emerged as points of a consolidated discourse, which self-referentially reified European academic ways of knowing and the knowledge gained about the objects of continued study. The growth of colonialism and global capitalism reinforced these dynamics while disseminators of ideology included the schools, the mass media, the religious organizations, and the business sector, which all breathed in and breathed out what was effectively one consistent message (Althusser, 1970/2001).¹ The message implied the superiority of European civilization and ways of knowing. The West set itself up as the core and that was very soon unchallengeable. In fact, to challenge it was unthinkable. As Tuhiwai Smith (1999: p. 55) explained, about Enlightenment logic, “[d]eeply embedded in these [modernist] constructs are systems of classification and representation, which lend themselves easily to binary oppositions, dualisms, and hierarchical orderings of the world.”

The importance of core-periphery logic to Western understandings of geography and meaning can be seen via the island group called Orkney Islands in Scotland. There is an island called The Mainland, which is only slightly larger and more central within the group compared to a number of other islands (Philip's, 2011: map 109). Then the north-south aspect can be seen via two small islands being named South Ronaldsay and North Ronaldsay, although there are a

¹For more on global capitalism, in the imperialistic form that emerged in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, see *Imperialism: The Highest Stage of Capitalism* by Lenin (1969: pp. 169-263).

host of other islands in between them. The Mainland is seen as the important core of meaning and ideas, the north and south are the extremes of the periphery, still part of “us”, but only just, and fated to be administered and controlled by the core, the seat of all superior knowledge. So, Orkney has a Mainland, although it is subordinated to other Mainlands, located far away “down south” in Edinburgh and London.

This paper, inspired by Althusserian Marxism, feminism, social anthropology, and cultural criminology (DeKeseredy, 2011: pp. 51-55; Presdee, 2000), aims to highlight problematic areas in the field where the resilience of both European ways of knowing and colonial social hierarchies need to be decolonized.² I acknowledge an interesting point made by Moosa-Mitha (2015: p. 90) that a researcher may choose to occupy a position within the normative-critical-mainstream-difference-centred axes (see the Figure 1 in her book chapter) different from what the dominant expectation of that researcher’s theoretical perspective might suggest, since theories are “more about movement” than “rigid classification”. This is an important point in relation to Marxism where a researcher might want to move its ideas more in a difference-centred and/or anthropological direction, where meaning is found embedded within discourses and practices, but still remains open to interpretation (Moosa-Mitha, 2015: p. 90). I also note the word of caution expressed by Sullivan (2003: p. 41): “We embody the discourses that exist in our culture, our very being is constituted by them, they are a part of us, and thus we cannot simply throw them off”. Clearly, this applies to non-Indigenous white researchers, such as me, who have worked with Indigenous people in places such as South East Asia and Oceania, and their relations with European culture. It also applies, to an extent, to the *interpretations* that these researchers make about the Indigenous cultures studied. The problems faced by non-Indigenous researchers in locales such as South East Asia, East Asia, and Oceania include 1) failing to understand and fully respect embedded Indigenous cultural traditions and practices; 2) misconstruing or failing to grasp accurately underlying cultural practices that the researcher observes; 3) relating to the second point, looking at local cultural practices through a Western, rational, modernist lens that puts the individual and the nuclear family outside or above society; 4) sharply separating in their imagination data from context; and 5) regarding the Indigenous people and context as objects of study rather than co-partners in knowledge-creation and understanding. Other problems include 6) not being sufficiently embedded within or very close to an Indigenous village or other community organization; and 7) regarding a research project as something with a definite start and finish date and as something separate from both self and relations with others.

I use Michel Foucault’s (1980a: p. 133) ideas of “regimes of truth” and dis-

²A suitable definition of decolonizing is the first of two provided by Oxford Languages Online: [to] “free (an institution, sphere of activity, etc.) from the cultural or social effects of colonization; eliminate colonial influences or attitudes from”. The example provided by that source is: “the museum is closing some galleries as it embarks on an effort to decolonize the institution”.

course as the foundation for many of my arguments and critiques. Discourse, for Foucault, must be distinguished from language. Language refers to “the meaning of words, or rather the intention behind the words spoken or written” (Manning, 2015: p. 211). Discourse is the commonsense understandings of the world that express themselves through language, which then enforces hegemonic understandings (Manning, 2015: p. 211). By continued utterance, these discourses may effectively become materialized practices (Hook, 2001: p. 537). As Moosa-Mitha (2015: p. 83) explains, “we are socially produced by performing our truths in the many ways that we engage and participate in society”. There are competing socially-produced truths, but some will be dominant and others subjugated (Foucault, 1980b: pp. 81-83) or marginalized depending on who that particular society awards the right to speak. As Brock (2003: p. xiii) writes, “deviant designation can be used to suppress, contain, and stigmatize difference [within that society]...how the rules come to be made and who gets to be “normal.”

Why study practices? Because they embody meaning and assumptions about the world and then, by repetition, they help to reproduce the social world at the level of the everyday. Chambon (1999: p. 59) backs this up by saying: “By examining concrete practices in their most minute details, we can question institutional mechanisms and gain a new understanding”. Winch’s (2005: p. 181) comment adds a link to texts as follows: “Data” should be “drawn from ‘practical texts’ that provide rules, opinions, and advice on how to behave in a certain fashion...texts are themselves objects of a ‘practice’ in that they are designed to underpin everyday conduct”.

The stark reality is that the social hierarchies of the colonial era, embedded deeply in people’s subconscious through socialization processes, still stay intact into the postcolonial era. As the radical feminist Monique Wittig (1992) has said, our minds are also colonized territories. Whites tend to be on the top of social hierarchies (although their numbers may be small), with part-whites second (as in Fiji) and the Indigenous people often last or second-last (as in Singapore and Fiji), sometimes situated just above an underclass of foreign workers on short-term visas (as in Singapore and Hong Kong). In richer societies (as in Japan and South Korea), one might argue that the dominant ethnic group becomes the ruling-class and upper strata of society or, as in exceptional cases, such as Fiji, an emergent third group, such as the Fiji Indians, becomes the new middle or business class. Whites that stick together in their own small communities, and/or those who visit in whatever capacity, often replicate the lifestyles and logic of the colonial era, where the locals continue to be the exotic/patronized others. Sometimes, local ethnic groups reinforce the social hierarchies of colonialism to their own detriment (Moosa-Mitha, 2015: p. 82). White Europeans, as in Fiji, find it hard not to be seen as the leaders of social interaction and taste by themselves and by others.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The next section explores issues of Indigenous empowerment within my call to collaborate with Indigen-

ous researchers in the field, rather than just using them as interviewees or sources of data. The third section looks at governing myths and mythscapes. The fourth section considers philosophical issues around the concepts of “Where is here, where is there, who are we, who are they?” The fifth section looks at the issue of the European gaze and the reverse (or Indigenous) gaze. The sixth and last section of the paper is a brief Conclusion section.

2. Working Together with Indigenous Researchers in the Field

Genuine engagement and the desire to empower are the first steps to a decolonizing, antioppressive (Moosa-Mitha, 2015; Potts & Brown, 2015), insurgent (Gaudry, 2015) methodology. Research participants should be raised to positions such as expert adviser, co-researcher, co-interviewer, and vetter and approver of research product (Potts & Brown, 2015).

The village elders and headmen (or equivalent) should know of and support the project and receive the researcher’s ongoing respect and recognition, including gifts, that can be seen as a kind of tribute or tax for being on Indigenous land and receiving Indigenous support. My observations relate not only to researchers from the former colonial power, but to situations of wealth and power imbalances, such as Japanese, Chinese or South Korean researchers working in countries such as Fiji, Papua New Guinea or the Solomon Islands.

Usually, the researcher (hereafter: the foreign researcher) will require ongoing culturally-specific support to access interviewees and communities (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 27). It should be a small step then to allow the local adviser (hereafter: the local researcher) to play a major role in planning, conducting, and evaluating the interviews and participant-observation sessions (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 35). They then are not merely an interpreter/translator or even a facilitator, but become a genuine co-researcher who later on should be awarded with co-authorship on published work (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 19). This then begins to Decolonize and Indigenize the research project, at least from the data-collection stage onwards, as Indigenous logic, values and beliefs begin to imbue, colour and direct the research process.

The local researcher should start each interview as they have the background and cultural knowledge and will be skilled in building rapport, in culturally-specific ways, with the interviewees (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 35). The foreign researcher may then become more of a note-taker and speak less in the interview than the local researcher. The foreign researcher should be listening and watching intently to the discussion, the interaction and the ambience (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 29) They may focus on theoretical or global questions rather than culturally-specific ones demanding cultural knowledge, even for proper posing of questions and choosing of words. Sensitive questions too could be handled by the foreign researcher as that person is not so entangled with local cultural obligations and can walk away unscathed. Part of the interview may be conducted in the local language/dialect, with the local researcher translating either at the time

or later on. This requires that the foreign researcher trust the local researcher in terms of ability and integrity. However, this relinquishing of temporary control (Potts & Brown, 2015) may be a source of worry, concern, anxiety or even socially-learned guilt. Despite this, the local researcher will nearly always understand the local context and culture better and deserves a free hand so as to effectively begin to decolonize the methodology.

Choice of interviewees, order of interviews, and place and time/date of interviews could also be primarily decided upon by the local researcher(s) in conjunction with study participants (Potts & Brown, 2015: pp. 27, 35). Etiquette and standard practice, regarding seating positions, interview locations, modes of dress and address, the mood or atmosphere of the interview, and the type of humour that is culturally-appropriate, will be better known and understood by the local researcher(s) and local interviewees than by the foreign researcher(s) (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 35). The foreign researcher should often keep quiet at the start of and early on in the interview, be quick to adapt, and make sure that they do not violate cultural rules. They can ask questions to clarify things after the interview is over (with the local researchers), or, better still, ask questions before the interview begins (for example, on the journey to the interview site).

In the field, the foreign researcher(s), almost deliberately, out of necessity, becomes more of a junior partner in the research endeavour (Potts & Brown, 2015: p. 40, n. 4) although, in the university office setting, that relationship may reverse itself or become one of effective equality, despite the trappings of office. If the local researcher(s) is unsettled by being given so much leeway, this process can be done slowly or subtly so that the local researcher(s) naturally grows into her or his role. As Potts and Brown (2015, p. 30) explain, “figuring out how to enable individuals to participate, as they would wish, is challenging”. Local people researching with local people is always a desired outcome, with the foreign researcher operating largely in the note-taker/recorder/observer role, but, of course, after the interview, she or he can be free to offer interpretations of interview data and ask questions of the local researcher. However, any tendency towards a patronizing attitude is clearly unacceptable within decolonizing methodology, and each researcher and interviewee must be constantly alert to the spirit and tone of all interactions, including interviews and discussions.

3. Governing Myths and Mythscapes

Duncan Bell (2003) was concerned by how the idea of collective memory has taken on increased significance within history, sociology, anthropology, geography and cultural studies. That author believes that the overreliance on the shadowy concept of collective memory, raising it up to a self-evident truth, but still shrouded in mysticism, means that the social process by which myths are constructed, and whose interests they serve, gets overshadowed. Bell dismisses the idea that collective memory can be handed down from generation to generation. He limits collective memory to collective remembrance, which occurs when a

group of people get together to remember or commemorate a past event which each one witnessed.

Bell (2003) introduces a social agency approach which keeps collective remembrance and mythscapes as separate things, which means that it is then possible to contest the dominant narrative or governing myth of a nation, group or other community. While, in practice, there may be common elements between collective remembrance and the mythscape, it is important to remember that these things are distinct. The mythscape is defined here as the “page” (Bell, 2003, p. 66) on which alternative myths fight out the battle for ascendancy and dominance. A governing myth cannot be so readily challenged if it is presented only as a (reified) collective memory. Hence, we should distinguish collective memory from the mythscape.

The governing myths of postcolonial countries in many cases reveal British logic, or the logic of the occupying colonial power in the particular case, with their discourse assumptions, presumptions, ways of thinking and knowing, values and order. These remain extremely difficult to dislodge and residuals, or even pretty much the complete myth, lingers on. But local myths and interpretations circulate too, and often the remaining Europeans either are unaware of them or let them continue on as a local curiosity. At other times, the resident Europeans may choose to take on a quasi-local identity, by endorsing the local myths, clearly wanting to separate themselves (ostentatiously sometimes) from more transient Europeans (e.g., tourists). A complex and controversial example might be the British-influenced culture of Hong Kong lingering on under Chinese rule after 1997, including cultural and legal practices, such as driving on the left-hand side of the road, and British-styled institutions. Some practices are deeply embedded and merged with other, local ways of doing things. For example, can we trace or separate out the British influence on Hong Kong public libraries and churches from local and other influences? Other situations are equally complex, such as Northern Ireland and Israel/Palestine. Singapore Airlines has been criticized by some locals for treating European customers better than Singaporean customers, and the Singapore Girl image arguably caters to Western fascination with the Orient that includes an overt sexualization of local women. In Indonesia, we see obscure American heavy metal bands attracting huge crowds whereas, in their home countries, they may attract only small followings. An example is when Testament met the mayor and played in front of fifty thousand people in Kalimantan. Although local Indonesian bands do modify this Western style of music to fit local aesthetics and topical issues, the respect shown to a Western-derived musical form, as opposed to the distaste shown towards local musical *dangdut*, reflects colonial-era hierarchies and European logic, although much of this process may be subconscious.

In Fiji soccer, important myths revered until today include the May 1985 Fiji national team’s 3-0 friendly win over Newcastle United and its November 1988 1-0 win over Australia at Prince Charles Park, Nadi. The second victory is prized locally as a case when the arrogant regional power, Australia, was humbled by

the islander minnows and their pride brought low. Clearly, the reverence paid to both these victories presents Fiji as noble and determined underdog, strong of heart and pure in spirit. As such, the victories are indisputably racialized. And, of course, Fiji's losses (2-0 to Newcastle three days later and 5-1 to Australia in Australia one week later) are *deliberately forgotten* and prevented from entering the mythscape. So, here we have relatively powerful local myths that still circulate as *renegade memories*, underneath the governing myth. The myths continue to be promulgated as oral traditions within the soccer community, with Ravuama Madigi unchallenged as soccer icon because of his great goal against Australia.

These myths are kept intact in basic meaning over many years, but the details are allowed to vary, and no-one seems to mind. This in itself may be seen as a protest against Western rationality. For example, the final score in the first Newcastle United game is sometimes presented as 3-1, 5-0, or 5-1. Even these noted variations have a purpose—they either exaggerate the score or they magnanimously “allow” the visitors a consolation goal as a display of local benevolence. The 5-1 may be because people remember the 5-1 score in the second 1988 Australia-versus-Fiji match and apply this to the 1985 Newcastle United game. The point of the myth is the convincing win, and so nobody thinks that the myth is invalidated if people get the score wrong or goal scorers' names wrong, whereas, in European logic, information is either correct or incorrect, and to include an error may well invalidate the entire content. This is never the Fiji understanding. If someone wants to check scores, they will either call someone who played in the game or, occasionally, refer you back to the historic newspapers. As the newspapers are not online, but stored in the *Fiji Times* office in Suva, a four- or five-hour bus trip away from Western Fiji, the newspaper collection is rarely consulted by anyone—the point is that it exists, “over there” in Suva, as a silent referee (Big Other) on competing claims.

At an interview, conducted by Henry Dyer and the author with ex-Fiji player, Meli Vuilabasa, who played in the Australia match at right-back (Dyer & James, 2023: p. 43), Vuilabasa said that the ex-players had been waiting for someone like me to come to hear their stories. Although I was working in Fiji at the time, I think what they meant was a white Australian. This could partly be because of the colonial penchant to record, rule, interpret, and observe, and so Indigenous people internalize this behaviour (and let the recorders do their recording). But, in this case, the motive was largely that Fiji beat Australia in that match and this was a rare event. It was due to wanting recognition for their exploits, against the odds, against a far richer and better resourced team who were upset by the defeat but avenged it a week later. The second match, won 5-1 by Australia, has no place in the mythscape of Fiji soccer, it is just a depressing example of financial and sporting might that tells us no story worth telling. *A reverse of colonial logic will always be more important than another demonstration of colonial logic.*

We move on to look at the 1983 South Pacific Games, in Apia, Samoa, when the various island team members divided themselves into English-speaking and

French-speaking with the English countries supporting Fiji and the French supporting Tahiti in the soccer final (Dyer & James, 2023: Chap. 3, pp. 47-59; James & Nadan, 2020: pp. 749-750). In one way, this reflects learned socialization and the continuation of imperialistic rivalries within a postcolonial setting. But these identities are no longer threatening in this context: Western nations are not interested in the event; and there is a postmodern playfulness. However, the actions might be construed as false consciousness by some postcolonial writers (Gavey, 1989: p. 471). But Indigenous people use such identifications for their own enjoyment and empowerment at the times and contexts of their choosing, they are almost subverted into being “subaltern myths” (Bell, 2003: p. 74).

The German manager of Fiji, the late Rudi Gutendorf (1926-2019), and the Fiji players were concerned about the partiality of the French-speaking officials for the final and Rudi’s presence may have helped cement the strength of the anti-French feelings. So, the identification was also a way to marginalize and other the French officials in the context of a heated soccer rivalry. While Indigenous Fijians acknowledge certain oneness with other Indigenous groups, the principal perceived contradiction here was specified in terms of English and French. And they took on those full identifications too—“English” and “French”—rather than just “English-speaking” and “French-speaking” or ex-colony status. While these could be seen as just shorthand, I think there was also a desire to playfully usurp the actual identities of English/French. Those involved would think that they had earned the right, and who was watching anyway? In soccer terms, there was a genuine fear of what the French players and officials could do (some Tahiti stars had played in the French leagues) and this was a cause and symptom of the marginalization of the “French”. Expectations were fulfilled, as a late Tahiti goal was followed by a riot in which the Fijian players played major roles (Dyer & James, 2023: pp. 52-57). While this story may be baffling to postcolonial researchers, it reveals lived reality on-the-ground in postcolonial times. A Eurocentric interpretation of this story, where the Indigenous people are *solely* trapped into postcolonial identities, would not do justice either to the complexity of the situation or the degree of agency shown by the Indigenous athletes.

These myths (above) also reveal the forms of Indigenous knowing (Tuhiwai Smith, 2021: p. 79), where the score does not really matter, only the victory matters, losses are willfully forgotten without guilt, and kindness and grace are shown by giving the losers a consolation goal that, according to the erstwhile newspaper of the era, never happened. By contrast, European knowledge requires accurate historical records of the score, the goal-scorers, and the minutes of play in which the goal-scorers scored (European time is linear and one-directional), the best players list, and an official attendance count. Without these, we don’t have acceptable knowledge, just stories, fragments, memories, subjugated knowledges.

Other Indigenous forms of knowing (Tuhiwai Smith, 2021: p. 79) include the playful use of European identifiers (English, French) in remote contexts, far from Westerners’ eyes, when the identifications are used to dramatize a con-

temporary sporting rivalry by adding a layer of imperialistic meaning to it (in addition to other meanings amidst a sense of Indigenous oneness).

Another example relates to a gay white Australian man who would visit Fiji regularly and buy beers for Indigenous men as part of a seduction routine. His style and manner were disliked by many Indigenous people. “He was beaten up”, Francis once told me in passing at the former Deep Sea Pub in Nadi (now closed)—no details were offered and no evidence was presented, I was expected to accept the fact based on trust in his word and the relentless force of logic and morals which dictated that bad things happen to bad people, almost without a subject to enforce it. *The disappearance of the subject*, I thought to myself, *Foucault would be well pleased*. While bashing of gays, for reasons of sexuality, is deplorable, the important point of this story is the fact that the story does not have a subject, other than the relentless force of village logic, and the fact that there are consequences for acting contrary to Indigenous manners and culture.

4. Where Is Here, Where Is There, Who Are We, Who Are They?

One of the racist remarks made by white trade-union official Eddie Booth in the BBC television comedy series *Love Thy Neighbour*, to his black neighbour, Bill Reynolds, was “we discovered you, you didn’t come and discover us”.³ The ideological force of this statement, and its individual words, should be immediately obvious to anyone and its power was indeed obvious to Booth who found its logical unassailable. Within European, modernist understandings of the world, the statement is, or perhaps was, unchallengeable, commonsense, and even (socially) true by definition. The words imply core-periphery understandings, but also white civilization, white bravery, white earnestness to learn about the world and record it for future generations, and nonwhite (alleged) lack of direction, lack of fortitude, lack of desire to know, and lack of technical expertise. The key words are we, you, us, and discover. The word “discover” implies European ways of knowing, understanding, classifying, journeying and behaving. Since nonwhites often have different systems of knowledge and discovery, they are excluded from the so-called race (pun intended) before they can begin. Although left-wing academics (such as Edward Said), and many others from other political positions, might challenge these notions, and have done so, at least in their more directly-expressed forms, consider these questions: We accept that British people can research in Africa or Oceania (subject to caveats on mutual respect, etc) but how would we react if an African, Asian or Fijian person wanted to come to Britain to research Britain? Wouldn’t we (the British) scoff and think: what could that person possibly add to what *we* already know? “We” can go overseas to research “them”, but “they” can’t come to research “us” (or even, arguably, study European minority communities in their own countries).

³The series ran from 1972-1976. Eddie Booth was played by the late John Smedhurst (1932-2022), while Bill Reynolds was played by Rudolph Walker. BBC refers to British Broadcasting Corporation (not Barbados Badminton Club) although you already knew that!

A white British person can freely research (say) Pakistani immigrant communities in Glasgow or Leeds, but can a Pakistani-Scot (even one born in Glasgow) research the “white people” outside of a topic about racism or gender issues? If she was a business student, a deracinated topic, such as cryptocurrency or the ethics of microbusinesses, could be embarked upon, with racial references removed, but researching “white people” as a distinct topic area might prove harder. What about when nonwhite researchers “bypass” and “ignore” “us” such as when (say) a Chinese student researches a Malaysian or Indian topic? Do “we” get offended? Surely “we” must be consulted and our expertise sought and all parties “must” put the research within European hierarchies and cultural forms, by quoting European experts in the field, etc. These presumptions are deeply ingrained in the subconscious of European peoples, and many others around the globe, and are hard to challenge.

How often do people with English given and family names get quoted as gurus and pioneers in their field, while authors with non-European given and family names get silently “dropped” from the canon, as the years pass, if they were not already ignored right from the beginning? Appadurai and Chakrabarty might be good examples here. Do they get cited less as the years pass? An example from popular culture (and there are many others) is the silent removal of the black guitarist Jimi Hendrix from the approved and endorsed history of heavy metal music.

Another aspect of dominant ideology concerns the words “here” and “there”, where “here” has always meant the colonial power and its metropolis (London or Paris) while “there” is assumed to be the opposite of what “here” represents. “Here” is presumed and presented as the source of knowledge, civilization, wisdom and recordkeeping so one’s standing as being from “here” and speaking from “here” is always, already unassailable. No-one from “there” is allowed to speak for “here” except, possibly, in the case of a person from “there” who was born and educated “here”. That person is then assumed to be fully socialized with the knowledge and culture of “here” and hence ready to extol the greatness of “here” and the weakness of “there”. Examples of “there” include Eastern Europe, Russia, the Middle East, Africa, India/Pakistan and Oceania. A person from “there” may be permitted to write and talk about “there” but only if they recognize the “there-status” of “there” and position their work within core-periphery logic. The attraction of immigration to the Global North, and especially to Britain, lies partly in the imagination of generations of Nigerians or Indians who were socialized about not only the greatness of Britain, but its irrevocable and unquestionable “hereness”. Nigerians may feel lacking as long as they are away from the “here” that has been talked about and revered in Nigeria for generations. Racism, poverty, disappointment and substandard jobs and housing in Britain are unlikely to lead the person to want to leave because the existence of Britain in the imagination (Araujo, 2018) is irresistible and vital to self-identity and understanding of the world. As Urry (1990: p. 13) wrote about tourism, people want to go to places in real-life because they have already been

there in their imaginations. The islands of Oceania were and are the ultimate in “thereness”, and suffer today from the high cost of imported goods of all types (as opposed to local services performed by wage-labourers) and the limitations this poses for economic development. As the opposite of “hereness”, they are popular for tourists from “here”, but few want to migrate to or contribute to life in the islands long-term, despite their desperate need for capital and skilled labour.

To sum up thus far, “we discovered you” implies that “you” don’t have the ability to discover because “you” don’t keep proper records and “you” don’t create or control the canon. “You” have no right or ability to “discover” “us” as “we” are “here”, “you” are “there”, far away. “You” can’t come and discover the “centre” as “we” already know about it. If you write for your own people, it will either replicate Western discourse or be an idiosyncratic, local peculiarity - in both cases “you” will be ignored by “us”. Susan Hanson (1999: p. 138) writes that: “Feminist geographers struggle to hold together the sometimes competing and contradictory realities inherent in these local-to-global geographic dimensions of relevance”. In other words, locals might conclusively believe that a social issue is of high social relevance, but academic authors (including the local and the foreign) find it hard to persuade global readers, especially in the Western countries, that there is a global relevance to an apparent local curiosity.

Just as Connell (1995, 2000) wrote about “patriarchal dividend”, there is unquestionably, although it varies from context to context, a “white dividend”, whereby a white foreigner is able to get better access to people or communities for interviews, than local researchers, when researching in a postcolonial country. In my experience, this is especially true of Indonesia and Fiji. Tuhiwai Smith (2021: p. 10) points out, too, that, if given a choice, Indigenous communities often prefer to work with a non-Indigenous researcher than an Indigenous researcher. In Indonesia, it can be hard sometimes to separate this “white dividend” effect out from Muslim hospitality and Indonesian respect for elders, but it is worth assessing each situation to try to understand dynamics and causal factors. There is the excitement of someone new coming from overseas as well as the imagined idea of Britain that has been transferred from generation to generation in the former colonies and at home. Britain could, and still can, position itself in people’s imaginations as the centre of the world in a way that even France can’t emulate. The tremendous recent success of EPL (English Premier League) football around the world is a prime example. The white researcher may find that local people are more willing to give extended interviews and more of their time to them than to a local researcher. This creates a dilemma because the “white dividend” may be concerning or even distressing to some foreigners but it undoubtedly helps them greatly with their research. It is disingenuous to deny it or pretend it doesn’t happen by relegating it to the subconscious, because ideas relegated to the subconscious can cause more harm as they spread their effects out like a trail of debris. Even in this situation, the foreign researcher should continually aim to decentre and dismantle assumptions and empower both local

researchers and local interviewees. Colonialism continues on in the mind (Wittig, 1992), and this is a tricky situation with which the foreign researcher may feel complicit. As these are systemic issues, there is no point becoming distressed about them, and energy instead should be devoted to building strong long-term relationships (Tuhiwai Smith, 2021: p. 15) with locals (and other foreigners) and empowering locals. The researcher should think in terms of “us” as everyone, without moving into areas that might be seen as cultural appropriation. The world of (say) Indonesia should become the “new here” for the foreign researcher who (usually) then returns to living in the now “new there” of Britain, Australia, Canada, New Zealand or the USA. Some researchers, and I am one, put so much energy and enthusiasm (and so much of themselves) into overseas field-work that they return to the Global North and can’t face moving on to a new project. So, they continue on with the old one, following up on various extensions, amplifications and updates. They may also feel a sense of guilt at leaving friends and research participants “back in the islands” while they return to the Global North.

Longing for the country of one’s fieldwork can provoke an unimaginable sense of loss and lack, an inner feeling that one is locked out of an important part of oneself. But lack of money, teaching commitments and lockdowns may prevent trips back. Few authors, to my knowledge, have written about post-research project emotions that can take on forms that appear illogical and extreme. But a trip back can sometimes bring disorientation as the place one used to know has changed irrevocably in one’s absence—people have died or moved on and, as a result, group dynamics and cultures have changed. I then was faced with the realization, in the heart now as much as in the head, that the period of my fieldwork was akin to a moment in time. The certainty that I once had had vanished and the new, young crowds in the nightclubs I didn’t understand. My old local friends hadn’t seemed to have fared much better—they too looked lost at sea.

After two publishers agreed to publish our co-created memoir of the Fiji soccer legend, but did nothing, I bit the bullet and decided to pay an ex-student in Fiji (now a junior lecturer) to get fifty copies of the book printed locally. This was my ethical commitment to the ex-player and his community. The book was published eight years after the project had ended, but it was a case of better late than never. As Tuhiwai Smith (2021: p. 16) writes, “[s]haring knowledge is also a long-term commitment”. I had published journal articles based on the memoir and could have just walked away and there would have been no comeuppance from the legal or academic viewpoints. But I felt I owed this ex-player and his community the chance to hold finished copies of the book in their hands as they had invested so much time and energy into this project.

5. The Issues of the Gaze and the Reverse Gaze

Issues may emerge out in the field when interviewing or accessing married or single women, and this is told from the perspective of the European-origin straight/male researcher. Problems can arise from the learned feelings of en-

titlement that the general acquiescences to foreigners may exacerbate. The welcoming attitude towards guests in a country such as Indonesia and the response to mere difference can sometimes be interpreted as literal displays of postcolonial hierarchies and deference. While postcolonial social hierarchies exist, they merge in complex ways with local hierarchies and nothing can be presumed upon without more detailed cultural knowledge that mostly arises from lived experience. To present oneself as asexual may be dishonest so this presents existential challenges for researchers. There is also the moral, religious policing gaze in Indonesia. People have a habit of gazing at white foreigners - the curious gaze, the bashful gaze, the teasing gaze, the interested gaze, the hostile gaze, the respectful/fraternal gaze (acknowledgement of shared humanity despite cultural and linguistic differences). It can be easy to tire of the gaze, become self-conscious, or adopt idiosyncracies/mannerisms/nervousness if one has self-esteem issues. This is more likely to pose a problem for younger researchers. Gaze becomes more obvious outside tourist areas and city-centre areas and may be close to nonexistent in places such as Hong Kong. And the researcher is always gazing back at locals.

Misunderstandings can emerge in the context of resentment towards the foreigner's greater spending power and their supposed access to the trappings of a bourgeois lifestyle that includes air-travel and four- and five-star hotels. These silent resentments, if they occur, are the responsibility of the researcher to manage, not the responsibility of research participants. Consumption should be hidden and inconspicuous in places of poverty out of a sense of respect for the other and so that lingering resentment doesn't have fertile ground to breed.

Resentment can lead to banter, joking, teasing, avoidance, or, very occasionally, outright hostility. An Indonesian anarchy-punk rocker teased me mercilessly once for staying in the bourgeois Holiday Inn in Bandung and I took the teasing on the chin and never ventured back to that hotel again! (My "crime" was made worse by the Holiday Inn being only a short distance away from a favourite drop-in centre for punks and activists, The Common Room Network Foundation.) Resentment can increase if the researcher is seen to be pursuing sexual or romantic liaisons with local women or men in a way that is culturally-inappropriate or seen to be taking advantage of one's bourgeois status and lifestyle. Sending money to someone (even if reimbursement for expenditure or for a service such as translation work) can be misinterpreted by others. I would recommend that a foreign researcher who wants to send money to a local woman for work done in relation to a project do it via a trusted local mutual friend. As was mentioned, the answer is not to present as asexual, but to be restrained and to make sure sincere relationship-building is seen as a priority over pursuing the two types of liaisons mentioned.

Very often, the reasons for someone's gaze must remain a complete mystery to everyone but the gazer, so it is inadvisable to over-think these things, although if a given relationship is presumed to be fractured, every effort should be made to repair it, regardless of whether the person is still actively contributing to your

research project or not. Some possible motives for the reverse gaze are: tempting you to pride/testing your groundedness/forcing you to prove yourself over time/hiding resentments over inequality, colonialism, or attacks on Muslims by the West. There is nothing at all wrong with at least the second and third one of these. I have had people refuse to shake my hand in a Jakarta bar and had bad looks from a few older men in the street in the deeply religious Indonesian city of Bangkalan. Both of these events occurred in the 2011-2014 period. These looks probably reflected anti-Western sentiment arising from the Iraq and Afghanistan wars and the foreigner just has to accept this and deal with it calmly and internally. The only acceptable response is to smile and walk away. In fact, many researchers from Western countries agree and accept that Muslim-majority countries have been persecuted, by “their” governments, in the name of the “war on terror” that was aimed at the alleged “axis of evil”.

6. Conclusion

This paper, written by a non-Indigenous ethnographer with experience working with Indigenous people in the Fiji Islands and Indonesia, aims to provide some thoughts and insights into decolonizing methodologies. I started with reflections on the importance of empowering Indigenous participants to take on the roles of co-researcher and co-interviewer, so that rapport can be established with Indigenous interviewees and a dialogue between locals can emerge which trades on and raises to the surface culturally-based knowledge and interpretations. The foreign researcher becomes largely a note-taker and observer of interactions, body language and atmosphere. Later on, the researchers can discuss the interview and provide a mixture of observation and interpretations, but seen primarily through the lens of the local researcher.

Then I went on to discuss the idea of governing myth within a mythscape and how alternative myths circulate within Indigenous communities that give pride of place to the achievement of locals especially when put up (as in soccer) against an opposition representing a colonial power. And the 1983 South Pacific Games story shows Indigenous people taking on English and French identification in a context, time and place of their own choosing as part of a postmodern playing with categories that added meaning and enjoyment to the here-and-now.

The next section explained how ideologies of imperialism appeared and still operate with the key idea being Britain as the centre of the world, the “discoverer” of nations of the periphery, the “here” where “we” live, as opposed to the “there” where the colonized people speak from (only to be usually ignored at the same time as knowledge about them gained by Europeans is fitted into European knowledge categories).

The last section on the gaze talked about the (reverse) gaze of the Indigenous upon the foreign researcher and how this reverses the continued imperialistic gaze of the foreign researcher upon the locals. It is unnerving and can be due to resentment against colonialism, the bourgeois lifestyle and privileges of the

white researcher or, in recent times, the anger at Western nations for the “war on terror” and the invasions of Iraq and Afghanistan. The reverse gaze, in my view, very often means that the foreigner is under pressure to prove their character and good intentions over the longer-term. If that is the case, then the reverse gaze is entirely justified.

The non-Indigenous researcher must learn to build sincere long-term relationships with not only research participants but their extended families and friends and identify completely with their struggles to such an extent that “us” is all-inclusive and “here” becomes “there” and “there” becomes “here”. There may then be an ache in your soul that is never filled once you leave your fieldwork country. People must not be used in an instrumental fashion, meaning that one must not operate with the intention of sucking the knowledge out of them and then casting them aside. As they are custodians of the land, we are only in the country with the Indigenous people’s implied permission. And, after colonialism, the moral debts are all ours to repay. *The researcher does not get the permission to walk away at any time*, where “walking away” takes on the meaning implied in the Anglo-American ethics approval forms used at Anglo-American universities, *i.e.*, the willful cutting off of ties.

Lastly, it might be worth considering how the mass media influences the decolonizing agenda. Firstly, social media, with its anti-slavery and pro-feminism currents in recent years, has forced a rethink by Western governments and people about the negative effects of colonialism, and exploitation in general, and related to this has been various moves to decolonize art and museum collections and education syllabi. Also, efforts have been made to foster diversity and inclusion and the fair and just treatment of Indigenous peoples. Countries such as Barbados and Jamaica, in the Caribbean region, have prioritized becoming republics by removing the British monarch as their Head of State ([Office of the Prime Minister, Government of Jamaica, 2023](#)). The left-wing mass media, such as *The Guardian* in England, has championed decolonization causes, while the right-wing mass media has been mixed, with some policies, such as the UK’s planned deportation of asylum seekers to Rwanda, being very controversial and attracting strong reactions from both sides. Recently, the renewed Israel-Palestine conflict has divided communities across the globe including in Britain.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Althusser, L. (2001). Ideology and Ideological State Apparatus (Notes towards an Investigation). In B. Brewster (Trans.), *Lenin and Philosophy and Other Essays* (pp. 85-126). Modern Review Press. (Original work published 1970)
- Araujo, N. (2018). Engendering Cosmopolitanism: Gendered Narratives of Instability and Agency. *Women’s Studies International Forum*, 67, 102-109.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2017.06.001>
- Bell, D. S. A. (2003). Mythscapes: Memory, Mythology, and National Identity. *British Journal of Sociology*, 54, 63-81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0007131032000045905>
- Brock, D. (2003). Moving beyond Deviance: Power, Regulation and Governmentality. In D. Brock (Ed.), *Making Normal: Social Regulation in Canada* (pp. ix-xxxii). Nelson Thomson Learning.
- Chambon, A. (1999). Foucault's Approach: Making the Familiar Visible. In A. Chambon, A. Irving, & L. Epstein (Eds.), *Reading Foucault for Social Work* (pp. 51-82). Columbia University Press.
- Connell, R. W. (Raewyn) (1995). *Masculinities*. University of California Press.
- Connell, R. W. (Raewyn) (2000). *The Men and the Boys*. Polity Press.
- DeKeseredy, W. S. (2011). *Contemporary Critical Criminology*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203869239>
- Dyer, H., & James, K. (2023). *Henry Dyer Remembers: My Life in Soccer*. Eliva Press.
- Foucault, M. (1980a). Truth and Power. In C. Gordon (Ed.), *Michel Foucault—Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977* (pp. 109-133). Vintage.
- Foucault, M. (1980b). Two Lectures. In C. Gordon (Ed.), *Michel Foucault—Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977* (pp. 78-108). Vintage.
- Gaudry, A. (2015). Researching the Resurgence: Insurgent Research and Community-Engaged Methodologies in 21st-Century Academic Inquiry. In S. Strega, & L. Brown (Eds.), *Research as Resistance: Revisiting Critical, Indigenous, and Anti-Oppressive Approaches* (2nd ed., pp. 243-265). Canadian Scholars Press.
- Gavey, N. (1989). Feminist Poststructuralist and Discourse Analysis: Contributions to Feminist Psychology. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 13, 459-475. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-6402.1989.tb01014.x>
- Hanson, S. (1999). Is Feminist Geography Relevant? *Scottish Geographical Journal*, 115, 133-141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702549908553822>
- Hook, D. (2001). Discourse, Knowledge, Materiality, History: Foucault and Discourse Analysis. *Theory & Psychology*, 11, 521-547. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959354301114006>
- James, K., & Nadan, Y. (2020). Race, Ethnicity, and Class Issues in Fiji Soccer 1980-2015. *Soccer & Society*, 21, 741-761. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14660970.2020.1742706>
- Lenin, V. I. (1969). *Selected Works: A One-Volume Selection of Lenin's Most Essential Writings*. Lawrence & Wishart.
- Manning, E. (Eli) (2015). AIDS, Men, and Sex: Challenges of a Genderqueer Methodology. In S. Strega, & L. Brown (Eds.), *Research as Resistance: Revisiting Critical, Indigenous, and Anti-Oppressive Approaches* (2nd ed., pp. 199-219). Canadian Scholars Press.
- Moosa-Mitha, M. (2015). Situating Anti-Oppressive Theories within Critical and Difference-Centred Perspectives. In S. Strega, & L. Brown (Eds.), *Research as Resistance: Revisiting Critical, Indigenous, and Anti-Oppressive Approaches* (2nd ed., pp. 65-95). Canadian Scholars Press.
- Office of the Prime Minister, Government of Jamaica (2023). *Government Committed to Jamaica Becoming a Republic*. The Office of the Prime Minister, Government of Jamaica. <https://opm.gov.jm/news/government-committed-to-jamaica-becoming-a-republic/>
- Philip's (2011). *Philip's 2012 Complete Road Atlas: Britain and Ireland* (3rd ed.). Philip's.

-
- Potts, K. L., & Brown, L. (2015). Becoming an Anti-Oppressive Researcher. In S. Strega, & L. Brown (Eds.), *Research as Resistance: Revisiting Critical, Indigenous, and Anti-Oppressive Approaches* (2nd ed., pp. 17-41). Canadian Scholars Press.
- Presdee, M. (2000). *Cultural Criminology and the Carnival of Crime*. Routledge.
- Said, E. (1978). *Orientalism*. Vintage Books.
- Sullivan, N. (2003). Queer: A Question of Being or Doing? In *A Critical Introduction to Queer Theory* (pp. 37-56). Edinburgh University Press.
- Tuhiwai Smith, L. (1999). *Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples*. Zed Books.
- Tuhiwai Smith, L. (2021) [1999]. *Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples* (3rd ed.). Zed Books. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781350225282>
- Urry, J. (1990). *The Tourist Gaze: Leisure and Travel in Contemporary Societies*. Sage.
- Winch, S. (2005). Ethics, Government and Sexual Health: Insights from Foucault. *Nursing Ethics*, 12, 177-186. <https://doi.org/10.1191/0969733005ne774oa>
- Wittig, M. (1992). The Straight Mind. In *The Straight Mind and Other Essays* (pp. 21-32). Beacon Press.